

General state of the industry now and next steps

Since Loise Brown was born 43 years ago, more than 10 million have been born around the world today. Assisted reproductive techniques were proposed, from the beginning until now, for couples with fertility problems. The social users of ART -with no medical reasons- are increasing over the years. The mean age of women in the EU giving birth to their first child was gradually growing and stood at 29.4 years in 2019, according to Eurostat (in a range from 26.3 in Bulgaria to 31.3 in Italy in EU member states). Work and lifestyle in Europe can push women to delay their plan to have a child, which may also affect the expectations experienced that lead woman to ART. There is also some new evidence that contamination is affecting fertility. These factors, and others, are behind the high increase in demand for these techniques.

This exponential increase in demand has transformed an eminently clinical sector into a large commercial enterprise. The line between the public and private interest is blurred, and the regulation of practices by the authorities is not an easy task in a sector where scientific evidence does not find a decent home. From an ethical perspective, there is an essential tension between maximizing benefits -commercial mood- and quality of care -biomedical perspective.

Accessibility and affordability are also crucial, principally -but not only- in developing countries. In a nutshell: What is the relationship between the public health system and the private sector? How is the relationship between doctors and patients? What should be the role of authorities in the private sector? What impact does the incursion of clinics into large commercial enterprises have for the practice of reproductive health? What is the relationship between medical and professional ethics and economic policies? All these questions, and many others, must be approached scientifically to get a global idea of the implications of assisted human reproduction in society and its impact on the next generations.

B2-InF begins by exploring how young people understand, react, and interact with reproductive technologies and analyze the information offered by clinics to society. To align the information given by clinics with and for society through practical guidelines will empower citizens in their decisions and illuminate other ongoing research to comprehend better-assisted reproduction. In this field, the individual, technical and social dimensions are indissoluble.